

FURTHER INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE SYSTEM FOR CREATING A SAFE ENVIRONMENT AND EARLY PREVENTION OF OFFENSES IN MAHALLAS

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Abstract: This study comprehensively analyzes the issues of creating a safe environment in mahallas and further enhancing the effectiveness of the early offense prevention system. The importance of adapting preventive mechanisms to modern requirements in the context of contemporary threats, timely identification of root causes of crime, implementation of targeted measures, and the introduction of digital technologies is substantiated. Additionally, the study highlights opportunities to increase prevention effectiveness by strengthening the mahalla institution, defining specific responsibilities of the "mahalla seven," developing social partnerships, and implementing a strict accountability system. The study's conclusions demonstrate that creating a safe environment and harmonizing early prevention mechanisms are the main conditions for sustainable crime reduction.

Keywords: safe environment, early prevention, mahalla institution, criminogenic situation, social prevention, digital technologies, public cooperation, accountability, legal awareness, targeted measures.

In recent years, large-scale reforms have been carried out in our country to introduce fundamentally new mechanisms for ensuring peace and tranquility, eliminating the causes and conditions of offenses through social prevention, and forming a sense of personal security among the population. The legal framework in the field of public safety has been strengthened, the prevention system has been institutionally reformed, and the role of the mahalla institution has been further strengthened. However, the increasing complexity of social relations, the expansion of the information space, and global threats require further improvement of the prevention system.

Creating a safe environment in mahallas means not only reducing the level of crime, but also reliably protecting the life, health, and property of citizens. A safe environment is not only the absence of crime, but also the formation of a sense of stability, trust, and tranquility in the population. From this point of view, the improvement of the system of early prevention of offenses is an urgent task.

The "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 No. UP-158, defines as a priority task bringing the system of ensuring public safety and prevention to a qualitatively new level. Also, the Law "On Crime Prevention" and the Public Security Concept clearly defined the powers and responsibilities of responsible agencies and institutions. Defining "Early prevention of offenses in every mahalla" as a priority task in 2025 will serve to further deepen the prevention system at the mahalla level.

In 2024, the practice of determining quarterly targeted measures to stabilize the criminogenic situation in each mahalla where crimes were committed was introduced. This

approach is aimed at increasing management efficiency by assigning responsible managers at the mahalla-district-regional level and assigning specific sectoral responsibilities. This system provides an individual approach based on the real situation in each mahalla.

Conducting scientific and practical studies in mahallas with a difficult criminogenic situation makes it possible to identify the real causes of offenses. Crime is often associated with unemployment, weak social control, family problems, and low youth employment. Therefore, the prevention system should be aimed not only at the consequences, but also at the causes. Targeted measures serve precisely this purpose.

Defining the specific responsibility of each member of the "mahalla seven" in preventing offenses committed by youth, women, and the unemployed in mahallas will increase the effectiveness of prevention. By early detection of crimes committed within the framework of family and domestic relations, constant work with prevention facilities, and provision of social assistance, negative situations are prevented.

Raising the legal awareness of the population, strengthening civic responsibility, and involving the public in the preventive process are important conditions for creating a safe environment. By widely involving representatives of the older generation, mahalla activists, and the public in solving social problems, an atmosphere of intolerance towards crime will be formed.

The introduction of modern digital technologies increases the effectiveness of the prevention system. The possibilities of early prevention and prompt response to offenses will be expanded through the integration of video surveillance, intellectual analysis, electronic monitoring, and information platforms. At the same time, establishing a system of strict accountability for the results of the activities of each responsible agency will strengthen accountability.

Thus, creating a safe environment in mahallas and increasing the effectiveness of the early prevention system requires a comprehensive approach. This process will be carried out through the harmonization of the legal framework, targeted management, social partnership, digital technologies, and strict accountability mechanisms.

Creating a safe environment in mahallas and further increasing the effectiveness of the system of early prevention of offenses is one of the priority tasks of public administration today. In recent years, fundamentally new mechanisms for ensuring peace and tranquility have been introduced in our country, a system of social prevention aimed at eliminating the causes and conditions of offenses has been formed, and comprehensive measures aimed at strengthening the sense of personal security among the population have been implemented. However, modern threats, the complication of social relations, and the expansion of the digital environment require constant improvement of the preventive system[1].

In the "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 No. UP-158, ensuring public safety and early prevention of offenses are defined as a priority area of state policy. Also, the Law "On Crime Prevention" and the Public Security Concept established clear legal boundaries for the activities of responsible agencies and institutions. Defining "Early prevention of offenses in every mahalla" as a priority task in 2025 will serve to deepen the prevention system at the mahalla level.

In order to stabilize the criminogenic situation in each mahalla where crimes were committed in 2024, the practice of determining quarterly targeted measures at the mahalla-

district-region level has been introduced. This approach forms a territorial and targeted model of prevention. In international practice, regional analysis and the "hot spot" approach have been assessed as an effective mechanism for reducing crime rates[2]. Assigning responsible managers at the mahalla level and assigning specific sectoral responsibilities will strengthen management discipline and enhance personal responsibility for performance.

Conducting on-site studies based on scientific and practical approaches in mahallas with a difficult criminogenic situation makes it possible to identify the real factors of offenses. Crime is often associated with social and domestic problems - unemployment, family conflicts, weak social control, and low youth employment. Scientific research has emphasized that preventive measures yield stable results when focused on causes [3]. Therefore, taking organizational and legal measures to eliminate the identified factors increases the effectiveness of prevention.

It is important to determine the responsibility of each representative of the "mahalla seven" in preventing crimes committed by youth, women, and the unemployed, as well as within the framework of family and domestic relations. Targeted work, identification of preventive facilities, and establishing constant communication with them strengthen the mechanism of early prevention. In particular, the early detection of cases of domestic violence and the provision of psychological and legal assistance prevent the aggravation of crimes [4].

Raising the legal awareness, social activity, and civic responsibility of the population is the social pillar of prevention. By involving representatives of the public, elders, and mahalla activists in the process of solving social problems, an atmosphere of intolerance towards crime will be formed. Sociological studies have noted that in regions with a high level of collective control, offenses are observed less frequently [5].

An innovative area of prevention is the widespread introduction of modern digital technologies in mahallas to create a safe environment in public places and residential buildings. Improvement of video surveillance cameras, intelligent analytical systems, "Safe City" platforms, and lighting infrastructure will reduce the likelihood of committing crimes. International studies have shown that video surveillance systems serve to reduce crime in public places [6].

An important factor in ensuring effectiveness is the establishment of a system of strict questioning of the results of crime prevention measures. Systematic assessment of the activities of each responsible agency, strengthening accountability mechanisms, and applying measures to address instances of irresponsibility will make the prevention system more disciplined and effective. In public administration, the "performance accountability" model is considered an important tool for improving efficiency [7].

According to official data, positive changes in the dynamics of crime are observed in areas where preventive measures have been comprehensively implemented [8]. This shows that creating a safe environment and harmoniously implementing early prevention mechanisms is the right direction.

Thus, to create a safe environment in mahallas and further increase the effectiveness of the early prevention system of offenses, it is necessary to implement targeted management, scientific and practical analysis, social partnership, digital technologies, and strict accountability mechanisms in harmony. Through this, it is possible not only to reduce the level of crime, but also to create an atmosphere of stable security and trust among citizens. Based on the foregoing, the following can be concluded:

1. creating a safe environment in mahallas is the main condition for a stable reduction in crime and requires the systematic introduction of early prevention mechanisms.
2. analysis of the criminogenic situation at the mahalla level and the definition of targeted measures will increase the effectiveness of management and will allow for the rational use of resources.
3. Defining the specific responsibility of the members of the "Mahalla Seven" and coordinating their activities will ensure the effectiveness of the prevention system.
4. Targeted work with youth, women, and the unemployed, eliminating family problems, can reduce the root causes of offenses.
5. the widespread introduction of digital technologies and the formation of a unified control system will expand the possibilities of early warning and prompt response.
6. an atmosphere of intolerance towards offenses will be formed in mahallas by strengthening public participation and increasing civic responsibility.
7. the establishment of strict accountability and polling mechanisms ensures the stable and effective functioning of the prevention system and strengthens a safe social environment.

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